

a) ASTRAL-III species tree for *orthologs.unfiltered* dataset



0.5

b) ASTRAL-III species tree for *orthologs.by.eye* dataset



0.6

c) ASTRAL-III species tree for *orthologs.HybPiper2.long* dataset



0.5

d) ASTRAL-III species tree for *orthologs.HybPiper2.no.warnings* dataset



0.6

e) ASTRAL-III species tree for *HybPhaser* dataset



0.5

f) ASTRAL-III species tree for *MO* dataset



0.7

g) ASTRAL-III species tree for *proportion.PI* dataset



0.4

h) ASTRAL-III species tree for *proportion.internal.branch.lengths* dataset



0.4

i) ASTRAL-III species tree for *average.BS* dataset



0.5

j) ASTRAL-III species tree for *tree.length* dataset



0.4

k) ASTRAL-III species tree for *bipartition* dataset



0.6